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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Políticas sociales para promover la actividad innovadora de las empresas ucranianas en tiempos de guerra

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Resumen

Se formula la definición del autor de la actividad de innovación, se revela la esencia del potencial de innovación y sus componentes: intelectual, personal, tecnológico, de investigación, financiero, infraestructural, organizativo y de gestión. Se describen los problemas del desarrollo innovador de la Ucrania moderna en condiciones de guerra que impiden el funcionamiento de la economía del país. Se concluye que para el curso estratégico del desarrollo socioeconómico de Ucrania es importante tener en cuenta la experiencia mundial de la metodología de formación de las áreas prioritarias nacionales de la ciencia y la tecnología, el desarrollo innovador de las empresas. La atención se centra en la viabilidad de utilizar en el proceso de innovación los logros de la industria de TI como la transparencia de la gestión de la información, la reducción de costes, los sistemas de gestión de las relaciones con los clientes, etc. Según los resultados del estudio, se han propuesto medidas para crear un entorno de orientación social para el desarrollo de las entidades económicas y fortalecer su competitividad a nivel nacional e internacional, el potencial del movimiento de inicio para garantizar la renovación tecnológica y el crecimiento económico del país se ha comprobado.

Palabras clave: política social, actividad empresarial, desarrollo innovador, potencial intelectual, startup, riesgos.

Abstract

Social policies to promote the innovative activity of Ukrainian companies in times of war

The author's definition of innovation activity is formulated, the essence of innovation potential and its components is revealed: intellectual, personnel, technological, research, financial, infrastructural, organizational and managerial. The problems of innovative development of modern Ukraine in wartime conditions that impede the functioning of the country's economy are outlined. It is concluded that for the strategic course of socio-economic development of Ukraine it is important to take into account the world experience of the methodology of formation of national priority areas of science and technology, innovative development of enterprises. Attention is focused on the feasibility of using in the process of innovation such achievements of the IT industry as

transparency of information management, cost reduction, customer relationship management systems, etc. According to the results of the study, measures have been proposed to create a socially oriented environment for the development of economic entities and to strengthen their competitiveness at the domestic and international levels, the potential of the startup movement to ensure technological renewal and economic growth of the country has been substantiated.

Keywords: emotional disorders, divorce, RDoC framework

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1. Introduction

As the history of the development of society shows, the rapid development of social innovations and their variants arises in times of various social, economic, ideological, natural crises, etc. The core of the crisis is always the contradiction between what is and what should be according to the needs of time. As external factors that induce the introduction of innovations in the social and other spheres, any changes in society, in the social structure, economic, ideological changes, international projects, political priorities, etc. are revealed.

At the modern stage of development of many countries, one of the most urgent tasks is the reproduction of social, human and labor potential and the formation of an innovative environment for the successful solution of this problem. Topical issues are the implementation of social innovation processes - changes occurring in complex systems that can be caused by both external sources and internal mechanisms of development. One of the main catalysts for such development is rightly called social innovations aimed at the harmonious, balanced development of man and society and the effective use of human capital.

Practice shows that in those countries that have chosen a socially oriented type of development, it is social innovations that form an innovative environment that promotes scientific technological and information innovations, ensures their acceleration, increases the efficiency of using new technologies, and reduces innovative costs. Conversely, where there is a contradiction between the stated social goals of state policy and real actions, conflicts arise, the degree of distrust in society increases, and social problems

worsen.

In the context of the rapid change of the modern world, a new non-standard idea, innovative technologies, scientific developments and research, globalization of markets, etc. are at the forefront of the development of the world economy. In particular, the efficiency of the investment process is the basis for the successful functioning of the state economy and individual enterprises. It is the innovative direction of development in recent decades that is the strategic benchmark of the country's economy.

Intense competition, constant expansion of the range of goods and services and increasing the requirements for them on the part of consumers and other factors require the adaptation of each individual business entity to maintain leadership positions in certain market segments. One of the effective means of achieving such goals is the functioning of the enterprise on an innovative basis. This problem is of particular relevance in connection with Ukraine's approaching to join the European Union. And that is why a significant part of enterprises develop strategies for introducing innovative solutions into their activities in the long term (Bodnaryuk, 2023).

Military operations in Ukraine have a significant impact on the country's innovation environment. The war led to significant economic challenges: to reduce the level of investment, increase the risk to business and reduce domestic demand for products. A significant number of technical experts and innovative entrepreneurs left the country during the conflict, which led to the loss of technical expertise and a decrease in the number of innovative projects. Unprovoked conflict and economic difficulties have reduced the availability of financing for innovative projects in Ukraine (Klymash, 2023).

Among the key factors that hinder the inflow of investments, scientists also highlight insufficient funding for innovative projects, lack of favorable legislation, low level of qualification of specialists and infrastructure for innovation, lack of human and intellectual capital, corruption, currency instability and inhibition of reforms, inefficient judicial system, issues of allocation of land and reimbursement of value added tax, overcoming technical barriers to trade and customs procedures (Slastyanikova, 2020; Kushnir, 2020; Poklonskyi et al., 2021; Bielialov et al., 2023).

During the war, business focused on the social component of sustainable development. According to modern research, the main priority of business is to support employees and their families in matters of relocation, payment of wages in case of forced downtime, compensation for families of wounded as a result of hostilities (97%). The respondents identified the support of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and the Territorial Defense Forces (84%) and the provision of humanitarian support to internally displaced persons (69%) as important priorities (EBA, 2023). Among other things, the acceleration of these processes will be facilitated by the social policy of promoting the innovative activities of Ukrainian companies in the conditions of war.

So, it is important to determine the main priorities of Ukraine's social policy in promoting the innovative activities of Ukrainian companies under martial law. The research of innovation activity as a factor of world integration and pilawar recovery of Ukraine is relevant, it can be useful for the development of strategies to support innovative enterprises and public policy in the future. The key factor in Ukraine's economic recovery after the war may be innovation.

2. Methodology of the study

To fulfill the tasks and achieve the goal, the scientific article uses a complex of modern methods of scientific research, namely: theoretical generalization - when studying the essence of the concepts of "social policy" and "innovative activity"; classifications - when determining the main types of innovations; comparative analysis - in determining the advantages and disadvantages of various sources of financing the innovation activity of the enterprise; methods of financial analysis - when analyzing the effectiveness of economic activity under martial law; planning and forecasting - when developing proposals for the implementation of social policy to promote the innovative activities of Ukrainian companies in war conditions.

3. Analysis of recent research

In modern literature, much attention is paid to the study of innovation in a socially oriented society. As the analysis of literary sources has shown, in scientific works for the most part, general questions are raised regarding the concept of "innovation activity," issues of planning the innovation activity of enterprises, investment and innovation activity of industrial enterprises, financial support of such activities, etc. are also considered. Despite the indisputable scientific and practical value of the above-mentioned works, now the need to find directions for improving the social policy of promoting innovation under martial law is of particular relevance.

The purpose of the scientific article is to analyze the state of social policy and the effectiveness of innovation activity in Ukraine in conditions of war, to substantiate the theoretical and methodological provisions of the innovation activity of the enterprise, in particular, the creation and development of startups, sources of their financing, as well as the development of practical recommendations for improving the efficiency of the enterprise with an innovative direction.

4. Results and discussion

Effective innovation creates significant strategic advantages in the most competitive industries. Leading enterprises achieve competitive advantages through innovation through the use of both new technologies and working methods, but after achieving the advantages of maintaining them, it becomes possible only through constant improvements, that is, continuous innovation. Thus, at the present stage of the

world socially oriented economic development, the main feature of competitiveness is its innovation, that is, the system's ability to systematically develop, update and change in economic activity based on the assimilation of innovations.

It should be emphasized that the government of Ukraine in connection with the war updated the list of priority directions of innovative activity to the actual needs of the period of martial law and the needs of Ukraine's recovery. The Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine approved the Action Plan for 2022-2023, which will contribute to the implementation of the Strategy for the Development of Innovation Activities until 2030. Also, on 05.02.2023, the Law of Ukraine No. 2859-IX entered into force, which amended the laws of Ukraine "On priority areas of development of science and technology" and "On priority areas of innovative activity in Ukraine" regarding the extension of the priority areas approved by these laws for 2023 year (Sarkanych, 2023).

Innovation is an idea, the newest product in the field of technology, labor organization, management, as well as in other areas of scientific and social activity, based on the use of scientific achievements and best practices, is the final result of innovative activity (Boyko, 2018). Innovative activity is an activity aimed at finding, developing, introducing the results of scientific research into a new and improved product, service and process with their subsequent distribution for profit. To achieve the goal of innovation, it is necessary to search for new ways and opportunities, more rational use of available resources, the introduction of the latest achievements to meet the diverse needs of consumers. Innovation activities consist of scientific, technological, organizational, financial and commercial activities, which together lead to the creation of innovation (Kosovets, 2023; Nikitenko *et al.*, 2023).

The definition of the concept of "Innovative activity" is present not only in scientific literature, but also in normative acts: in the Law of Ukraine "On investment activity" (On Investment Activity, 1991), "On innovative activities" (On Innovative Activities, 2002), in the Economic Code of Ukraine (Economic Code of Ukraine, 2003). In particular, in the Law of Ukraine "On Innovative Activities" this concept is interpreted as an activity aimed at the use and commercialization of the results of scientific research and development and causes the release of new competitive goods and services to the market" (On Innovative Activities, 2002).

Analyzing the formed interpretations of innovative activity in doctrine and legal acts, it can be noted that a characteristic feature of any innovative activity is the generation of a product at the expense of scientific research or the use of new technologies and approaches in production. Based on this, innovative activity can be described as a set of measures aimed at the practical use of scientific, scientific and technological results of the available intellectual potential in order to create a new or improved product, technological process, methods of organizing production, work, organizational structure and management systems. Innovative entrepreneurial activity

is a special process of business organization based on the constant search for new opportunities to improve the technical and technological factors of production.

The concept of "social innovation" can be defined as a deliberately organized innovation or a new phenomenon in the practice of social work, which is formed at a certain stage in the development of society in accordance with changing social conditions and is aimed at effective positive transformations in the social sphere. The thematic publication Stanford Social Innovation Review proclaimed social innovation "a process of finding, providing support and implementing original solutions for social needs and problems" (Boyko-Boychuk, 2009). The sources of social innovation are changes in the external environment, social problems that constantly arise and that cannot be solved by traditional methods, as well as changes in the needs of society and its members.

Innovative social technologies are methods, means of innovative activity aimed at creating and materializing innovations in society, at implementing initiatives that cause qualitative changes in various spheres of public life, lead to the rational use of material and other resources in society. Of particular importance are innovative social technologies in crisis, transition periods, when the technology of social processes is almost completely changing and there is an urgent need to improve the production, management, political and spiritual spheres of public life".

According to some analysts, the main directions of innovative development of the industrial sector in post-war Ukraine can be: supporting foreign partners to preserve the existing research and innovation base, as well as creating new opportunities for Ukrainian startups and innovative small and medium-sized enterprises; development of a complex innovation policy that optimizes the structure of the innovation system and progressive forms of market institutions and creates a basis for the functioning of the economy; creating a favorable environment for innovative development through the implementation of state and regional policies aimed at achieving long-term socio-economic goals and reproduction of high-quality fixed capital; increasing the role of higher education institutions as an "incubator" of fundamental and applied research and development, as well as a place for the implementation of startup ideas (Economic truth, 2022). This can be achieved by financing the most attractive technologies, ensuring the interaction of higher education institutions with companies and other research institutions, as well as the formation of state support for the most promising projects.

With the successful implementation of the above-mentioned directions of innovative development, new development prospects will appear for small and medium-sized businesses in post-war Ukraine. In particular, it is the development of a strong and sustainable innovation ecosystem that can contribute to the socio-economic development of the country, the creation of new opportunities for Ukrainian startups and innovative enterprises by attracting investments from foreign partners.

In the right opinion of S. Zayka, the implementation of the innovation process is influenced by the following factors: high risk and uncertainty of ways to achieve goals; impossibility of detailed planning and orientation to forecast estimates; the need to overcome the resistance of the enterprise, both in the field of economic relations and the interests of the participants of the innovation process; dependence on the socio-economic environment in which the enterprise functions and develops (Zaika, 2015).

The result of innovative activity and development of the enterprise will be a continuous and progressive change in its quality, and whether the innovation process will be revolutionary or evolutionary will depend on the chosen innovative direction, effective strategy and level of innovative development, and what will be the ratio of intellectual resources and human intellectual capital in the future, which owns and/or employs a trade enterprise. A rational combination of the direction of innovation and development and the elements of the enterprise's intellectual capital can guarantee the advantages of the enterprise's economic development.

In the context of application in the IT sphere, the following general features of innovation can be distinguished: a high level of unpredictability of consequences, personnel dependence, creative nature of solutions, high labor intensity, and in some cases also cost, the need for an appropriate scientific and research environment, the presence of external barriers and internal resistance. Specific features are: territorial dispersion of personnel, high level of informatization, predominance of project and team forms of activity, active use of outsourcing, possibility of using foreign experience.

Innovations in the IT sphere are inextricably linked with technological innovations, which make up their technological basis. At the same time, it should be remembered that even in the conditions of the fourth industrial revolution and the development of information technologies, it is impossible to hope for complete automation of management functions, because such traits as leadership, experience, creativity, intuition, teamwork are unique to humans. Quality management, controlling, reengineering, system intervention strategy, neuro-network technologies, information-associative modeling, structural-functional modeling, etc. have already become somewhat widespread in Ukraine at the level of individual economic entities (Gorbachenko, 2021).

The humanization of economic growth is aided by social innovations in the economy, and their implementation and practical application have a positive impact on the stable and sustainable reproduction of vital forces of the entire nation, individual social communities, and specific people. So, today, enterprises of all spheres of the economy of Ukraine can use the following achievements of the IT industry in the process of implementing innovations: transparency of information management (enterprise resource management system; corporate portals; IT outsourcing; business analytics systems); reducing expenses, including reducing the cost of production (video conferences and unification of communications; enterprise resource management

system; IT outsourcing models; creation of a data processing center, centralization of resources); increase in circulation, including the development of relations with clients, regional development (business analytics systems; video conferencing and unified communications; customer relationship management systems; self-service systems, Help Desk, contact center).

To date, the issues of creating startup projects as a form of innovative entrepreneurship remain insufficiently resolved in theoretical and practical aspects. Currently, in Ukraine, we are observing the formation and development of incubation, acceleration and grant support programs for startups. Timely response to challenges in the conditions of war contributed to the emergence of new innovative projects in Ukraine, in particular: Raccoon.World – a Ukrainian startup that develops virtual reality therapy for patients with post-traumatic stress disorder (Raccoon – HealthTech, 2023); People's Project is a charity fund that helps raise funds for military and veterans in Ukraine (All-Ukrainian Center of Volunteers, 2023).

This list is not exhaustive and indicates that, under the condition of effective and rational management, innovative projects can be implemented even in extremely difficult conditions of war. After all, the management of innovative projects in the conditions of war should, first of all, contribute to the effective use of resources, ensure safety and the successful implementation of strategic tasks.

There are different ways to attract investments to finance startups. Among the main models of financing startups, the following are distinguished: franchise; venture funds; business angels; competitions; business accelerators; crowdfunding; Smart money (Kovalyova, 2014).

An important factor in the development of startups is demand from powerful investors and industrial enterprises. The main reasons for the lack of demand for startups in Ukraine are: lack of financial resources; insufficient information about existing projects; high risk; lack of market potential; lack of support from the state. The problems of investment and innovative development of Ukraine are systematically studied in works (Kasych, 2016).

In addition, startups in modern conditions need proper attention and support from both the state and enterprises that have been working on the Ukrainian market for many years and should be interested in the development of new, modern projects. Startups need a stable regulatory and legal environment, a healthy competition policy and a legal system that does not limit risk appetite; public financial support in the early stages of development, as well as co-financing schemes and tax incentives to help the wannabe in the emergence of private business angel or venture funding.

In the context of the socio-economic crisis, the development of startups will also be facilitated by a powerful education system and support for scientific research in

scientific institutions and higher education institutions that have a significant amount of scientific ideas, but due to the sensitivity of experience in this area and funding cannot get into the business environment. In Ukraine, the solution requires not only the issue of the low level of effectiveness of science in the form of patents, but also the problem of using the obtained patents in economic circulation, since the process of patenting scientific developments does not yet mean their commercial use. As the practice of the leading countries of the world shows, the creation of startups is an effective mechanism for attracting higher education institutions to the innovation process, determining the priorities of state financing of fundamental and applied research.

We believe that in this context, the following state-wide measures should become a priority: state assistance in establishing the "education-business-state" chain and increasing the level and quality of start-up education; increase of state investments in new projects; improvement of the legislative framework in terms of taking into account the interests of startups, in particular, regarding special preferential regimes; implementation of a stimulating program for the development of small and medium-sized businesses; promotion of increasing the activity of participation of Ukrainian entrepreneurs in international programs.

We share A. Dligach's point of view that effective post-war recovery of the country is possible only if appropriate state policy is carried out, including a liberal innovative economy (creating conditions for fair business competition and cooperation, attracting investments and forming a high level of trust in the state; development of human potential; stimulating the development of innovations and modernization (including digitalization) of the economy, barrier-free movement of capital and anticipatory development (recognition) of virtual assets, etc.) (Dligach, 2022).

In the context of the socio-economic crisis caused by the war in Ukraine, the development of a full-fledged innovation infrastructure in all regions will contribute to: paying significant attention to the factor necessary for innovative development - quality education; encouraging international cooperation that will facilitate the effective export-import of innovations, attracting additional funding from the European Union to improve the quality and effectiveness of innovation (Bielialov et al., 2023).

Thus, an effective and proven way to achieve success of the enterprise is its continuous development. This can be done thanks to the constant increase in the level of innovation. The government should be involved in providing an environment to support and help small and medium-sized enterprises to use information technology and increase the competitiveness, productivity and growth of countries by investing in information technology, e-business and new business models. Currently, Ukraine has significant unrealized opportunities in innovative development, using such advantages as the favorable geographical location of the country, a capacious market, a relatively high level of human resource development, and the presence of a deep and comprehensive free trade zone between Ukraine and the European Union.

5. Conclusion

According to the results of the scientific article, we can conclude that innovative activity is an important element of the development of the world, regional and national economy. Ensuring the stable innovative development of enterprises in Ukraine should become one of the priority areas of the state's activity, which will ensure the country's competitive advantages at the international level. It will also have a positive effect on the economy of the state in general, because the increase in the competitiveness of national producers will lead to an increase in the real gross domestic product, will improve the economic and social climate in the country.

Innovation activity is defined as a set of measures aimed at the practical use of scientific, scientific and technological results of the available intellectual potential in order to create a new or improved product, technological process, methods of organizing production, labor, organizational structure and management systems. Rational combination of the direction of innovation and development and elements of intellectual capital of the enterprise can guarantee the benefits of economic development of the enterprise. First of all, it is necessary to clearly define the state priorities of innovation activity in Ukraine and develop an effective set of measures for their implementation, which will include: financial incentives, creation of conditions for modernization of production, training of qualified specialists, involvement of research structures in the implementation of innovative projects, significant improvement of the general investment climate in the country.

Transformation processes in the social economic life and social political structure of Ukraine, aggravation of most social problems, requires the development of new approaches to their solution, leads to the need to find optimization of ways to solve social problems, the introduction of new concepts, methods and technologies for the provision of services. Hence - the main purpose of innovation in the social sphere should be the solution of socio-economic problems and state support in this direction. To choose a strategic course of socio-economic development of Ukraine, it is important to take into account the world experience of the methodology for the formation of national priority areas of science and technology, which usually consists of three interrelated processes: the formulation of the main strategic goal for the country, the consideration of generally accepted world priorities and the reflection of national characteristics, specifics of the country.

The creation and development of startups as a form of innovative entrepreneurship will be facilitated by the following priority nationwide measures: promoting the establishment of the "education-business-state" chain and increasing the level and quality of startup education; increase of state investments in new projects; improvement

of the legislative framework in terms of taking into account the interests of startups, in particular, regarding special preferential regimes; implementation of a stimulating program for the development of small and medium-sized businesses; promotion of increasing the activity of participation of Ukrainian entrepreneurs in international programs.

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